

EXPLORE LIBRARY ANXIETY AMONG UNDERGRADUATE ALLIED SCIENCE STUDENTS

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Abstract

Background: Library anxiety is a psychological barrier that limits students' effective use of academic libraries, particularly among undergraduate allied sciences students who rely heavily on scholarly resources for evidence-based learning.

Objectives: This study aimed to assess the level of library anxiety and identify its dominant contributing domains among undergraduate allied sciences students.

Methods: A cross-sectional quantitative study was conducted using a structured questionnaire to measure overall library anxiety and its sub-domains, including library environment, resources, staff interaction, user education, and user knowledge. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Results: The findings showed that students experienced mild library anxiety, with the library environment domain emerging as the major contributor, followed by library resources, while staff interaction and user knowledge contributed comparatively less. The findings showed that students experienced mild library anxiety, with the library environment domain emerging as the major contributor, followed by library resources, while staff interaction and user knowledge contributed comparatively less. Among 270 students participated, with 1st year students comprising 67 (24.8%), 2nd year 67 (24.8%), 3rd year 69 (25.6%) and 4th year 67 (24.8%). The overall mean library anxiety score was 2.94 ± 0.18 indicating mild anxiety.

Conclusion: These findings confirm that library anxiety among allied sciences students is primarily driven by environmental factors such as unfamiliar settings and discomfort within library spaces. Targeted improvements in library environment and structured orientation programs may significantly reduce anxiety and enhance students' academic engagement.

INTRODUCTION

Academic environment, while promoting intellectual growth and critical thinking, can

paradoxically create a high-stress atmosphere that leads to anxiety among students in this

highpressure environment students are susceptible to various forms of anxiety that hinder students' progress. library anxiety is a form of situational anxiety that occur in academic libraries and impede academic progress. Libraries are pivotal in academic settings, driving learning and research initiatives. The library impact on student success is undeniable, as it provides critical access to information resources that significantly influence academic performance¹. Anxiety is a complex response to perceived threats or dangers, often triggered by worries about everyday aspect of life, including health, work, social interaction and routine activities.² Library anxiety refers to the fear or apprehension students experience when using the library and its resources, Anxiety can stem from various factors including the library physical space and the process of finding material, While libraries are often seen as welcoming spaces for studying and research some students may find them intimidating, leading to feelings of anxiety.³ Library anxiety is the form of academic anxiety can significantly impact student academic performance, Moreover, Students ability to recognize and manage their emotions, as well as empathize with others, can influence the level of library anxiety.⁴ University libraries are essential to student success, providing critical support through instruction service and resources, By offering a conducive study environment, libraries enhance learning and contribute significantly to student retention and overall academic achievement,⁵ A key mission of academic libraries is to foster information literacy, empowering student with the skills to locate, evaluate, and utilize information effectively and ethically, thereby creating new knowledge.⁶ A library knowledge occur when students are unfamiliar with library resource, research technique or catalog system hindering their ability to find and use relevant information effectively.⁷ statistical analysis revealed significant association between variables, including 1) Staff interaction 2) Emotional barrier 3) Comfort level with the library environment 4) Library knowledge 5) Technical issues 6) Resource accessibility.⁸ Researcher have utilized the

Multidimensional Library Anxiety scale (MLAS) to help librarians mitigate library anxiety among students, However, some studies, particularly for undergraduate students later on due to rapid change in technology Anwar find MLAS of Van Kampen not suitable to study undergraduate student, The AQAK library anxiety scale has been identified as a reliable tool, boasting 90% reliability.⁹ The mean anxiety difference was less than the procedural cluster. This showed that the conceptual teaching had an effect on the conceptual cluster's mathematical anxiety ratings. The procedural teaching, which resembles the traditional methods of mathematics teaching, did not reduce the impact of the procedural cluster's anxiety¹⁰

Karim, Al-Huda, and Ansari conducted a study to investigate the level of anxiety among undergraduate students in Malaysia and to identify the factors contributing to library anxiety.¹¹

Adeeko and Adetimirin (2022) carried out a study to find the library anxiety of undergraduate students in north-central Nigerian universities. Seven hundred ninety-seven students were selected as a sample from a population of 15933. The measuring Scale on library anxiety (MSLA) developed by Bostick was used as a tool for measuring library anxiety.¹²

Hassan Ashrafi-Rizi (2014) conducted a study on library anxiety in two different Universities of Iran. He examined the factor affecting library anxiety of all students of Isfahan University of Medical Science (IUMS) and Shiraz University of Medical Science (SUMS). Major findings indicated that students of IUMS scored 2.68 and SUMS scored 2.66, which were found to be above average. He recommended that it is essential to acquaint students with academic libraries in the initial stage and suggested regular workshops in information literacy, user education, searching techniques, online information search etc. To familiarize university students with academic libraries, these methods can also be used to reduce their levels of library anxiety Prevalence of library anxiety.¹³

Ahmad, S., Ismail, M., and Khan, A Library anxiety has been the focus of study in many

countries of the world, particularly in the developing countries of Asia, but after going to the literature review, it was found that only a few studies have been conducted in Pakistan. Ismail et al. (2022) carried out a study to determine the level of library anxiety among management science students at the undergraduate level of the University of Peshawar using the AQAK Library Anxiety Scale. Two hundred sixty-two students were selected for data gathering. The study found that final-year students reported the lowest level of library anxiety compared to first-year students.¹⁴

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A Descriptive Cross-Sectional design was used for this study. This study was conducted at PUMHSW new campus, Nawabshah. This study was conducted at for 3 months after approval from Institutional Review Board (IRB) 270. Total population of this study consists of 1000 undergraduate allied science students enrolled in 1st yr to 4th yr at people's medical university of health science. The Estimated sample size is calculated with the help of Rao soft calculator. Margin of Error 5% Confidence Level 95%. Non probability convenient sampling. This study was conducted on undergraduate allied science students. Inclusion criteria included Students must be enrolled in DPT, PHARM-D, BSPH, BSN. Students must be people's medical university of health science. Students must voluntarily consent to participate in the study. Students who utilize the library's resources are often a target group for studies on library anxiety. Exclusion criteria included

Postgraduate students or those not pursuing an undergraduate degree. Students in non-allied field such as MBBS, BS cardiovascular technologist, BS medical laboratory technologist, BS intensive care technologist, BS anesthesia technologist. Students who are no longer enrolled or have already completed their studies. Students with specific health conditions unrelated to library anxiety. Students who are not actively attending the university. The data was collected through "Questionnaire" it consists of section A: Demographic information, (name, age, year of the study) Section B-F: AQAK scale consist of 40 statements assembled into 5 factors, library staff, library environment, informational resource, user knowledge and user education each statements measure library anxiety on a five points Likert scale ranging from 1-5. Library anxiety of undergraduate allied science students based on mean score. 1=No anxiety, 2= Low anxiety, 3=Mild anxiety, 4=Moderate anxiety, 5=Severe anxiety. Data will be analyzing by statistical package for social science (SPSS) latest version. The following statistical approaches will be used: Descriptive statistics: Determine the central tendency mean and dispersion (standard deviation) of demographic factors and library anxiety ratings. A confidence level of 95% will be used for the study. P value of < 0.05 was considered. The study was approving by Institutional Review Board of People's University of Medical and Health Sciences SBA. Informed written consent was taken from respondents. Confidentiality of the participant's information was ensured during data collection, analysis and interpretation.

RESULTS

Table 1: Academic Year of respondents

Academic Year	Frequency	Percent %
1st yr	67	24.8
2nd yr	67	24.8
3rd yr	67	24.8
4th yr	69	25.6
Total	270	100.0

Table 2: Factor-wise Descriptive Statistic for Library Anxiety

Sno	Sub Factors	Mean	SD±
1	Library Environment	3.07	0.371
2	Library Resource	3.03	0.229
3	Library Staff	3.03	0.134
4	User Knowledge	2.64	0.141
5	User Education	2.94	0.178

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Overall Library Anxiety

S.N	Statistics	Statistical values
1	Mean	2.94
2	Standard deviation	0.18

DISCUSSION

Regarding the demographical variables of this study, the mean age of participants figure1 was shown 20.99 ± 1.508 years, which is consistent with recent studies indicating that undergraduate students in this age group are primarily affected by library anxiety. This aligns with Ghanghro, who reported similar age range among undergraduates.¹⁵ figure 2 shows that most participants, 165 (61.11%) were from rural areas and 105 (38.89%) were from urban areas. This is similar to Hasanah, who found that students from urban settings had better access to library resources.¹⁶ figure 3 shows that participants, were almost equally distributed across 68 (25.19) were from DPT, 68 (25.56%) from Pharm D, 68 (25.19%) from BSPH, and 65 (24.7%) from BSN. Firdaus & Singh also reported that library is not discipline-specific and occurs across various health sciences programs.¹⁷ Table1 showed that most of the participants were distributed evenly across all academic years, 67 (24.8%) were from 1st year, 67 (24.8%) from 2nd year, 67 (24.8%) from 3rd year, 69 (25.6%) from 4th year, suggesting that library anxiety is present throughout undergraduate education.¹⁸ figure 4 shows that most participants, 38 (14.07%) visited the library daily, 92 (34.07%) visited weekly 140 (51.85%) visited monthly rather than daily. This align with Hasanah who observed that infrequent library visits were associated with higher anxiety levels, as students feel less confident navigating

library services.¹⁹ Table 2 shows the five domains mean, the library environment showed the highest mean score (mean = 3.07) followed by library resource (mean=3.03) and library staff (mean=3.03) user education domain had (mean=2.94), while the user knowledge domain recorded the lowest mean (mean= 2.64) this is supported Firdaus & Singh. Who identified environment discomfort and lack of confidence in research skills as major contributors to library anxiety.²⁰ Table 3 shows that, the overall mean score of library anxiety was 2.94 ± 0.18 indicating a mild level of anxiety among undergraduates, showing that these findings are consistent with Ghanghro.²¹

CONCLUSION

Library anxiety is a significant psychological barrier to effective library use and academic success characterized by feelings of confusion, and inadequacy in navigating library resources while staying in library this study was done in order to learn about library anxiety among undergraduate allied science students at PUMSHW, Nawabshah. Findings concluded that there exists mild level of library anxiety among undergraduate allied science students and there is no significance difference in anxiety level was found based on departments. Library environment are the most dominant sub-factors in creating library anxiety among undergraduates than other factors. which is mainly due to

unfamiliarity with the physical layout of the library, lack of confidence in navigating library spaces, and discomfort in approaching library staff, which collectively hinder effective use of library facilities and resource. Consequently, this possession of library anxiety can also impact other areas such as library avoidance or no use of library resources effectively. resulting in poor academic achievements of the students. Thus, this study concludes that for the improvement of library environment for better academic performance, the student should be free from library anxiety.

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